

Bioaccessibility of Arsenic in Mining Waste and Mining-affected Soils

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In vitro bioaccessibility tests are being used to evaluate the release of trace elements upon ingestion of soil, dust, and other fine-grained materials. In most cases, it considers fine-grained materials with varying chemical, physical and mineralogical properties, but it is not always clear how these properties influence the bioaccessibility of elements. The present study focusses on the bioaccessibility of arsenic (As) in mining waste and mining-affected soils. First, the results of a detailed study of the mobility (leaching tests), solid-phase speciation (SEM-EDS, XRD, LA-ICP-MS), and in vitro bioaccessibility of As in different types of mining waste and mining-affected soils are presented. Additionally, from the literature, data on the bioaccessibility of As in soil and mining waste samples were used to investigate the relation between chemical (element composition, pH, organic carbon content), physical (grainsize distribution) and mineralogical properties of the samples and the gastric and intestinal bioaccessibility of As. Stepwise multiple linear regression was performed to assess the relationship between bioaccessibility as a dependent variable, and (physico)chemical and/or mineralogical sample properties as independent variables.

The detailed characterization of the mine waste and soil samples showed that the mineralogical composition, specifically the content of Fe(hydr)oxides and arsenopyrite, played a significant role in determining As bioaccessibility. Overall, As displayed a low bio-accessible fraction, below 10% of its total content. Human health risk assessments, using bioaccessible As concentrations, indicated low carcinogenic or non-carcinogenic risks in case of (accidental) ingestion of soil or dust particles.

From the literature data, total As concentrations and pH were the most significant predictors of As bioaccessibility. Surprisingly, in only 7 of the 18 papers, information on the mineralogical composition of the samples was provided, and only 3 of the 18 papers provided quantitative mineralogical information. It was therefore difficult to explain bioaccessible As concentrations reported in literature using mineralogical sample composition. It is strongly recommended, in the context of bioavailability testing, to quantify the mineralogical composition of materials for which this is relevant and to share data in a more transparent manner.

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